

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan WP 7 Dissemination and Communication

13 - LEGAMBIENTE

Report

Public

Reviewers: BCN, NTUA, ZABALA

Version	Date	Description of main changes	Author
V1	2016-12-15		LEGAMBIENTE
V2	2017-02-16	Changes suggested by the PO included: reference to D8.3, include EU specific communication channels.	LEGAMBIENTE
V3	2017-07-04	Changes suggested by the PO, included deeper explanations	LEGAMBIENTE

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1. Context

Cities are becoming the places where important amount of resources are consumed and waste is generated: 2.7 billion tons of waste are thrown away in the European Union (EU) each year, of which 98 million tons are dangerous. Only 40% of the urban waste is re-used or recycled and the rest goes to landfill or incineration. In spite of communication campaign about recycling and saving resources, in the last 20 years municipal waste per person in Europe rose of about 15%.

Waste management is expensive, not merely in economic terms but also in environmental terms. The greenhouse gas emissions derived from municipal waste management are projected to decline by around 84 million tons of CO₂ equivalent by 2020; but in order to achieve this goal, further eco-innovative solutions need to be implemented.

Talking about urban waste as a new resource, should be an opportunity to aware first of all a deepest awareness about the problem and the possible solutions, thanks to new technologies, but also to create a chance in advancing policies and best practices among stakeholders (citizens, potential customers and investors of eco-innovative solutions, smart cities and research community, policy makers, etc.).

2. Objectives

The main objective of this plan is the diffusion of the concept that “The growing waste produced in Europe can be a valuable stock of resources and it is exploitable” to the largest number of targets, by using all the necessary communication tools and building a strong network of partners. In order to accomplish new strategic actions in this field, gathering data on waste management and sharing good practices among partners are essentials. Communication activities of the project are understood as a crucial key point for the success of the different pilots. For this reason the plan proposes to create a set of eco-innovative solutions by spreading the project’s pilots, in alignment with the EU Resource Efficiency Roadmap2 milestone: “By 2020, waste is managed as a resource”.

In order to guarantee the public coverage of the project results at the pilot level, knowledge and information transfer through multiple channels and networks will be coordinated and managed by WP4 and WP7.

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The communication strategy is oriented in two main axes:

- Target groups: who we need to achieve in order to get the maximum coverage for the project as well as an engagement from users in the local pilots
- Communication channels: how the target groups are going to be reached

A successful idea must be popular with the public. The more we will be able to promote the opportunities created by a circular economy and waste reduction attitude among associations, single citizens and stakeholders, the easier it will be the involvement of the institutions and policy makers. The general effectiveness of the project communication can be improved by promoting the program and informing people.

WASTE4THINK project will include also a large economical and social base: local business, enterprises, supermarkets, farmers, consumers and students, in order to involve as much people as possible in measures developed to maximize project impact.

The project communication will focus on building a strong network, from associations and public institutions to stakeholders and citizens. The implementation of the network will be realised by using partners' contacts, public relation activities and media. By specific networking initiatives, such as an official presentation of WASTE4THINK issues to other projects, periodical newsletters and a regular contacts update, it's possible to enlarge the joining to the network.

This Communication and Dissemination Plan has been defined in order to organize and evaluate the diffusion actions carried out in media and social network at Local, Regional, National and European levels. It is complementary to the Environmental Education Plan (D4.1) which will define the specific strategies to be followed during the implementation of each pilot in order to reach a high level of awareness and change in habits from the different targets involved, as well as the Exploitation Report (D6.2) which will include an specific Exploitation Action plan for each eco-innovative solution.

In general terms, the main objectives of the communication actions are:

- To raise awareness about the project (general communication activities)
- To raise awareness about the importance of a more efficient waste management
- To exchange experiences and best practices among partners

- To share technological and scientific results (dissemination activities as scientific publications and conferences, training materials and open data sharing according to the guideline described in Deliverable D8.3. Data Management Plan)
- To sensitize the general opinion and to make the local community more responsible to waste management and recycling systems.
- To make Public Institutions aware of the opportunity of save money moving to a more circular economy
- The co-operation between public institution and pilot will be decisive for the success of the project
- To promote H2020-programme and to strengthen its visibility. The general effectiveness of the project communication can improve by promoting the program and informing people
- To engage people in the project during its implementation. Specific dissemination material will be developed for each pilot to maximize the involvement of the neighbours
- To contribute to a corporate image of the exploitable results for their future commercialization

3. Target Audience

The definition of the targets is essential to study the right strategy and to point out the media tools to be used.

First of all, the targets could be different for each partner, in relation to the peculiarities of each Country. This represents a strength, not a weakness: in fact the more the targets are specific, the more the communication is widespread and successful.

After defining the targets, it will be necessary to set up the terms used to communicate with them, always linked with the networking activities

Which are WASTE4THINK targets? A general guide

The list below is a starting point, a more detailed description can be found in D1.1. Contacts, references and details about the following group will specify in the local communication plan written by each pilot, because each pilot has different contents and capability to reach, for example, stakeholders and Institutions in their Country and moreover each country has

different structure. The following list is a general guideline, useful to point out the right target of an effective communication for the pilot:

- **Direct users of the pilots.** This is the main target group for the pilots, that generally includes students and neighbors. Every pilot will define the number and characteristics of users that ensure its successful implementation and different communication strategies, necessary to involve them, following the matrix below. Selection criteria for people participating in the different actions within the project are described in Deliverable D9.6 H Requirement N° 5. This is quite an important target as the success of several social actions depends on their involvement, so special attention will be paid when issuing communication material and actions. Moreover, we have included in the Risk table (Deliverable D8.1 Project Management Plan) specific Risks (N°8 and N° 13) with their corresponding mitigation measures in case of lack of involvement or failure in reaching the specific audience.
- **Local institutions and policy makers.** For example: municipalities (not only the municipalities involved in the pilot, but also neighboring, municipalities in multi-utility network and municipalities involved in local waste management planning. All of these will be detailed in pilot individual communication plan), regional districts, political parties. They represent high-level manager at local and regional levels related to the localization of the pilots. It's important to involve them, because there are the subject responsible to define economic contributions for waste management, to guarantee hygienic and health standards, to choose companies and procedures in the local waste management and to point out policies on communication and education. Also, they are an important agent for the implementation of some actions, such as "Pay As You Throw" System, that requires a change in the local legislation.
- **Stakeholders.** This group contains relevant people at EU-level like other project representatives, the EC officers, Clusters and the overall community interested in Smart Cities and waste management as well as potential investors or funders for the future exploitation of the results. Attention will be also paid in the fulfilment of ethical requirements regarding selection of target groups, and disclosure of information, as detailed in WP9.6. In case any unclear aspect should arise during the communication and dissemination process, Ethical helpdesk assessment will be required.
- **Multi-utility companies.** They're involved in waste management starting from the collection to the treatment and the final destination.

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- **New potential municipalities involved.** Seeking for new members of the network in each Country can also be an opportunity to promote WASTE4THINK. It could be interesting to focus the attention in municipalities in urban, peri-urban and industrial sites, representing different kind of waste of medium-size environment and average of waste diverted to landfill. By involving these targets in the network it's possible to disseminate WASTE4THINK actions too.
- **Public Bodies.** The involvement of public bodies, at local and regional level of environmental, circular economy and recycling sectors, can contribute to build a network of innovative experiences.
- **Civil associations and NGOs.** The effort to enhance the relationship among associations with the same aims and challenges will give the opportunity to enlarge the number of selected contacts. This target will be involved in some results of the project, for example, Food App where NGOs will be entitled to collect the food surpluses from different producers.
- **Scientific community.** Researchers and Academics, specialists in the field that want to follow the project on-going and collaborate with further ideas, new suggestions, most recent developments, etc. Universities, technical stakeholders, companies involved in recycling and waste management, could have an interest in technological results of the project to improve or change their production system.
- **Journalists.** They are a key target group to let the pilots' results and news reach the general audience in the areas of execution. A database created by the pilot will include the more relevant names of journalists and media in order to properly reach other potential users and target groups.
- **General public interested in recycling and circular economy.** By involving interested people, it's possible to stimulate direct citizen promotion of changing the current urban waste management practices, through an informal approach (for example funny door-to-door team's actions).

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The following Table shows the tools that will be used for each target group. However, in order to find out the most efficient communication strategy, each pilot will adapt it taking to account their specific level of waste management, local communication and Environmental Education strategy and capability to reach the different target group.

Target groups	Direct users	Policy-makers/ Municipalities	Waste managers	Journalists	Stakeholders	Scientific community	Civil associations
Internet							
Websites	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	C	ALL
Social Networks	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL		ALL
Online promotion	ALL				ALL		
Apps (R5-7)	ALL		Z, C, S, H		Z, H		
Newsletter	ALL		Z, C, S, H	ALL	ALL		ALL
Event							
Pilot press conferences				Z, C, S, H			
Tour for journalist				Z, C, S, H			
Workshop	C	Z, C, S, H	Z, C, S, H		C	Z, C, S, H	Z, C, S, H
Dialogue days	ALL					ALL	
Final conference	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL
External event at EU level					ALL	ALL	ALL
General Media							
Press releases	C,	C, Z		ALL			

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Online articles	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL
Conferences				Z, C, S, H			
Promo videos	ZC, S, H	Z		Z, C, S, H			Z

Legend: ALL=partner of W4T project; C=Cascais; H=Halandri; S=Seveso; Z=Zamudio

Target groups	Direct users	Policy-makers and Municipalities	Waste managers	Journalists	Stakeholders	Scientific community	Civil associations
ZAMUDIO	Citizen, Commerce and Industry. Schools.	DFB, Basque Government Spain Ministry. Other municipalities and Commonwealth	Treatment plants, collection companies and clean points managers, townhall/commonwealth technicians	Local and regional TV, radio, newspapers and magazines	Technology providers, NGOs (social kitchens, food banks...),	Local universities and technological centers	Neighborhood associations
CASCAIS	Citizen, residents, services and school community	Cascais próxima (mobility) and Câmara Municipal de Cascais (town hall)	Tratolixo (treatment)	Local and regional TV, radio and newspapers	ONGs,	National universities	Residents associations, condominiums, local associations, sport/beach associations
HALANDRI	Citizen, residents, school community, commercial enterprises	Region of Attica, neighboring municipalities	Attica Association for Waste Management		ONGs, companies that can use the generated biomass product as raw material	Universities and research institutes	Local associations
SEVESO	Citizens, households, private enterprises, schools, nursery, parishes	Seveso Municipality, Lombardy Region	GELSIA, waste management company	Local and regional newspapers	Technology providers, NGOs, association organizing Eco-events, Recycling consortia	Universities and research institutes	associations, neighborhood

3.1 Interaction between WP4, WP5, WP6, WP9 and WP7

Since WP4 (innovative social actions), WP5 (new economical instruments) and WP6 (eco innovative solutions) deal with communication sensitization, it's important to create synergies among them and WP7 (communication and dissemination), in order to avoid overlapping.

WP7 has a general vision above all the project actions. Pilot's communication manager and each WP leader will be in contact with Legambiente, as WP7 leader, in order to match the provisions about tools and strategies contained in this Plan. Thanks to the Communication and Dissemination Plan overall guidelines are provided to lead pilots and project partners in their local communication. Communication manager working for project's pilot will be steadily in contact each other, by using email groups and online meeting (at least 3 at year) to match communication activities they are working on. In every operative documents WP4, WP5, and WP6 beneficiaries will foreseen a communication section according to WP7 leader.

Since WP4, WP5 and WP6 have a specific development and impact in a pilot territory, the communication strategies are tailor-made by the project partners, by using their websites, social networks and local media, in order to involve the targets pointed out. At the same time to communicate and disseminate the project activities and results the WASTE4THINK tools will be used. Each responsible of WP4, WP5 and WP6 will always take into account the communication tools and strategies in order to promote all the eco innovation solutions and social actions developed during the project. Communication materials of a social action or eco-innovative solution will be published and spread by each partner and then sent to WP7 leader. In collaboration with Aclima an archive of events and activities organised in the pilot territory will be created on WASTE4THINK website. Moreover, a communication strategy protocol has been established between WP4 and WP7 not to duplicate information nor work (see section 8. 3. Official Website and pilot website).

With regard to WP5, a strong communication activity has to be foreseen in order to assist the decision-makers in introducing new economic instruments in pilots. Some public events, press release, articles on media, on the web and socials have to be foreseen in accordance with communication manager when a new economic instrument, with the potential to change stakeholders' behaviour and habits, is being introduced.

In all communication and dissemination actions the fulfilment of ethical requirements regarding selection of target groups, and disclosure of information will be taken into consideration.

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The detail of all activities including a selection of the target groups is included in D9.6 - requirement n.5. If any unclear aspect should arise during the communication and dissemination process, the assessment of the Ethical helpdesk will be required.

The synergies between WP7, WP4 (innovative social actions) and WP6 (eco innovative solutions) are represented in the following scheme, already included in D4.1 (social action plan).

4. Project messages

Different objectives require specific contents in order to make an effective communicative action. In the following paragraphs there are some essential messages assigned to each target.

Message for local institutions, Municipalities and city Councils

→ *Resource efficiency improvements represent an overall saving for economy*

Circular economy systems keep the added value in products for as long as possible and eliminate waste. If we re-manufacture, reuse and recycle, we can move to a circular economy, where waste is eliminated and resources are used in a more efficient and sustainable way. Europe can benefit economically and environmentally from making better use of those resources. It is estimated that resource efficiency improvements all along the value chains could reduce material input needs by 17% - 24% by 2030, and a better use of resources could represent an overall **saving potential of 630€ billion per year for European industry**. Moving to more circular economic models promises a much brighter future not only for the European economy, but also for local economy and little municipalities.

The project is going to improve innovation capacity and integration of new knowledge and methodologies in the area of waste management in urban environments. WASTE4THINK approach itself is a relevant innovation in the sector, as knowledge in IT, education and social science will be applied to a demanding sector in order to demonstrate advanced eco-innovative solutions, with a clear direct application in urban environments, that could easily be extrapolated to other regions or other waste chains (e.g. technology parks, airports). This project will also accelerate the spread of innovative and technological solutions, and the public awareness with regard to urban waste production.

Message for environmental associations and NGOs

→ *Reduce to create values*

The sustainable planning of waste management strategies needs tools to support decisions at all stages of the process (generation, collection and treatment) with a holistic approach taking into account all the stakeholders involved. By integrating advanced waste management

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solutions WASTE4THINK will be in the position to monitor improvements in urban waste sorting (increase of a 20%), management costs (10% savings) or Greenhouse Gas emissions (reduction of a 10%).

The objective is moving towards the Zero Waste concept and contributing to achieve the Waste Framework Directive key principles (Proximity and self-sufficiency, Precautionary principle, Polluter pays principle, Waste hierarchy, Best Practicable Environmental Option and Producer responsibility).

Environmental impact associated with WASTE4THINK project is clear since the main objective is to pave the way for zero-waste systems by setting a waste data management methodology in different urban environments:

- Reduce CO₂ emissions thanks to: efficient collection routes; use of more sustainable vehicles and correct driving habits; traffic data and street properties; new waste management strategies based on re-use of some waste (nappies, food wastes) reducing CO₂ generation in comparison with incineration.
- Reduce landfill usage thanks to the promotion of reusing and recovery of materials.
- Improve recycling and recovery technologies.
- Prevention, dematerialisation, less energy and use of resources.

Message for general public interested in recycling and circular economy

→ *Turning waste into a resource*

The identification of the generation patterns and hot spots of the systems, the suggestion of improvement actions under a systemic approach and according to the needs and possibilities of each scenario, monitoring and evaluating the environmental, social and economic impact of the measures implemented, as well as social engagement by innovative education, awareness and information experiences (fostering mutual learning and citizen science) will have direct consequences over the reduction of waste in origin, the optimization of the waste infrastructures contributing to move towards a more equitable social system and the identification of new business and public governance models to take advantage of several urban and per-urban wastes. It is especially important that all that will contribute to minimize the environmental impact of the whole system, the decoupling of the economic growth from the use of the natural resources and the social empowerment building more sustainable cities.

Keywords:

- Zero-waste production
- Waste
- Resource
- Reduce
- Recycle
- Reuse
- Circular economy
- Share
- Experience
- Saving
- Nature
- Preservation
- Expertise
- Best practice
- Prevention
- Improving
- Recovery
- Technology
- Urban
- Emission
- Pollution
- Dematerialisation

6. Strategy and Activities

For a successful result it's essential to develop a strategy to take advantage from all the communication tools, in relation to the different targets the project wants to involve.

The municipalities, companies and associations involved in the project shall be pro-active to be a reference for the media in environmental matters, above all land recycling and circular economy issues. In this sense, the communication plan establishes the following steps:

First step: create attractive news

It's essential to give the news you want to spread through the media as catchy as possible. It's necessary not to wait for the journalists to ask for some news but to become a reliable source of information. All the project partners shall function as trustworthy sources in the communication system. The best way to be known as reliable source is to base the information you give on scientific data.

When you talk about the CO₂ emission, recycling, waste management and saving resources, you must add specific information about how many tons of urban waste are re-used or recycled and how many go to landfill or incineration, for example, or how much the

greenhouse gas emissions derived from municipal waste management and so on. Each press release has to be related with a specific message of WASTE4THINK project, taking into account the milestones of the project for themes and launching dates.

Second step: choose the proper Media

Based on WASTE4THINK contents and messages, it's necessary to find best local media and information channels in each different Country, in order to create a targeted and efficient communication.

What to do in details:

1. to evaluate your own knowledge of the media and to improve it if necessary.
2. to map local headings: TV, radio, newspapers, magazines, web sites, social networks. In the first phase each partner shall know how to deal with the information channels in its own Country. It will create a database of local (regional and national) media that partners can reach with communication.
3. to map all the local useful subjects. The knowledge of associations, committees, blogs, networks that work at local level in recycling, waste management and circular economy field can strongly contribute to a more widespread dissemination.
4. to arrange a contact list of journalists of regional and local headings (mail and phone). It's important to prepare and arrange and precise contact list. Having a direct relationship with the journalists is an added value. How to arrange a contact list:
 - To classify the contacts according to heading types: newspapers, magazines, TV, press agencies, radio, web sites and blog.
 - To add single local or regional headings, with the data of the editorial office, the desk, the managing editors, the journalists (for the biggest headings, there are specialised journalists) for each category.
 - To collect name, surname, mail address, telephone numbers (editorial office, mobile and fax) for each journalist.

Third step: define the best way to spread a message

Media can be useful for the dissemination of the project results but in a different way according with specific needs. It's very important to define the best way to reach the target of the message, in order to produce an effective communication.

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TV can reach a large number of people at the same time. It's important to use it only for big events with a high disposability of imagines. Radio can give information during the news or in a thematic programme. This second solution could be useful to introduce WASTE4THINK project, its aims and actions.

Since there is a large number of magazines and newspapers, first of all it's necessary to classify the generic ones and the specialised ones. The generic press asks for news, so it's better to use it only in case of a novelty, whereas it's possible to establish a long-term relationship with the editorial offices of specialised press. The aim is to implement networking activities and to promote the entire project. The specialised press is important for the activity of dissemination of results and best practices shared with partners of the project.

The local newspapers play an important role since they are widespread and read by many people.

Each partner has its own database of newspapers and magazines to contact, in relation to the event: local, regional or national.

For example: you can offer a better service to a journalist or an editorial staff of a television if you add to a press release also a video in HD standard with no graphics or logos, so they can use it for their reports. For websites and blogs, images are important tools to catch attention: for this reason each press release should be enhanced by at least with one photo.

Fourth step: share communication materials

Dissemination materials have to be shared with partners, following Consortium Agreement and Quality Plan, at least 30 calendar days before the publication, unless already public and/or earlier agreed. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

Fifth step: follow a communication agenda

The first launch of the project will be really important. Each partner shall use similar texts, according to project messages, integrated with specific contents about pilots and innovations,

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different for each partner and Country. The development of a communication agenda based on the activities of WASTE4THINK project and partners' initiatives is strategic. Thinking of press releases in such events can improve project dissemination.

For example: if there is a fair or an exhibition about recycling or circular economy, an important convention or meeting, at least a week in advance WASTE4THINK partners have to spread a press release related with the topic of the event, according to project message, enriched with local data to make the communication catchy and interesting for media.

After the first launch of the project, it's necessary to keep up the attention on WASTE4THINK. For each pilot action at least 2 press releases per year (total of 6 specific communication from the start to the end of the project) have to be edited, the last one to disseminate the results of the project. Once published, every press release must be collected on project's web site (sending the file to ACLIMA). Yearly each partner will send to ACLIMA also press reviews, in order to put on project's web site the collection of articles, TV reports, radio interviews, etc. of all partner involved.

Sixth step: use social network

A broad channel of communication is the social media network (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube). Each social media is peculiar and it can be useful for spreading a message. Project's partners have to use this channel in their communication in order to disseminate to a large audience the contents of the project and the innovation of the pilots.

For example: events should find in Facebook a favoured channel to involved general public, associations, groups and stakeholders. Photos of pilots and developments of the project can be spread through Pinterest or Instagram, using proper tags (see section KEYWORDS) and hashtags (there must be always #WASTE4THINK). Partner should post at least **one content per month** (photo, data, sharing articles or video from internet, graphics..)

Seventh step: enrich the communication with experiences

WASTE4THINK is quite technical, but the success of the project at the same time is bound to how general opinion receives the changing in litter production and waste management. WASTE4THINK communication can be improved by telling personal stories and involving people.

For example: organise tour with journalists, bloggers and a small selected group of common people to visit a positive model of installation of composting or paper and glass recycling system or a split-up system of litter (plastics, aluminium, polystyrene, metals). In this way they can be witnesses of changing and can spread the message that waste becomes a resource.

Eight step: organise project events

In order to reach all the target pointed out, partners shall organise specific workshops with relevant policy makers, waste managers and multi-utility companies, civic associations, researchers and Academics, to present project developments.

At the end of the project a final conference in Bilbao will be organised to present the results of WASTE4THINK.

7. Corporate Identity Manual

7.1. Communication management

Legambiente is in charge to coordinate the communication for the whole project, as WP7 leader. It will manage overall communications and project milestones.

Aclima is in charge of creating and managing the visual identity of WASTE4THINK Project. It will receive the contents of the pilots to publish them through the different channels of the project (web, social networks, newsletter, etc.).

If any of the entities within the Consortium wants to carry out a communication activity, they must communicate it to Aclima beforehand, so that it can be spread and recorded.

Please, all the entities involved in the WASTE4THINK project must register and inform about all communication and dissemination actions, by the corresponding sheet (See annex 1 and Dissemination google doc).

7.2. Patterns and design

An ad-hoc press release template will be elaborated with the aim for the remission of all communications regarding WASTE4THINK. The Press release will be headed by the WASTE4THINK logo and will mention all the entities involved in the project. Each pilot will manage demand from the media of its region (request for information, interviews, etc.) and it shall be brought to the attention of the coordinators of communication (Aclima) which will offer appropriate assistance and support in each case.

7.3. Media List

Each partner, especially the pilots, has to prepare a list with local/regional media, to whom disseminate the press releases, both the general ones and the ones specific to each pilot. These lists will be uploaded by partners in Redbooth platform.

7.4. Corporate Identity Manual

An image Corporate Identity Manual will be elaborated in order to define the logo applications in all the supports developed (See annex 3).

7.5. Languages

Overcoming language barriers and communication problems among partners is one of most important goal to achieve in the first part of the project. WASTE4THINK have to be also an opportunity to share good practices, results and strategies.

The official language of the project is English and therefore internal and external communication will be in this language.

However, since there is an important citizen participation in the project, for some specific issues the languages of the different regions will be used for the diffusion of messages at local level (press releases and social network).

At all times the pilots will be responsible for the translation of content into their languages. Some specifications about this:

- All materials will be in English. In addition, editable templates will be sent to the partners, so that they can translate them to their languages if needed.
- The website will be multilingual, being English the predominant language.
- The language in social profiles will be English. Nevertheless, within in each pilot space, network users and partners could interact in their own languages to foster participation.

7.6. People in charge with the Communication of the project

Each entity has to designate a responsible for communication of the Project who will be the link with Aclima for the reception and distribution of content.

i.e. table of contacts

Name	Surname	Entity	e-mail	Phone
Silvia	Valenti	Legambiente	ufficiostampa@legambientelombardia.it	+39 3498172191
Konstantina	Papadopoulou	NTUA	kpapado@chemeng.ntua.gr	+302107723115

This person should be accessible for any question arising out at communication level such as social networks interaction. In this case, the response should be prompt. The contact details will be available in the distribution lists uploaded in Redbooth platform.

7.7. Spokesperson

It is necessary that each project entity identifies a spokesperson among its collaborators, who would be the person in charge of speaking in seminars and conferences, if necessary. Besides, it would be responsible for conducting interviews in the media. The communication responsible is in charge of looking for the best candidate for each specific media appearance, depending on the approach of the seminar, conference, etc. (not only one person has to be designated). The selected candidate must have a good communicative skills. Names will be communicated to Legambiente in order to update the Communication and Dissemination Plan at M18 as expected in GA.

8. Tools

The communication tools and key elements are the following:

8.1. Corporate image

A logo and a specific corporate image have been designed for the Project (*see Annex 3*). WASTE4THINK logo is the peculiar element to easily identify the project. All the partners have to use it for their newsletters, websites, banners, posts on social networks and so on, in order to create a common style of communication.

A number of templates with the corporate image will be developed which have to be used by all entities in the documents generated in relation to the Project (*see Annex 4*).

8.2. Press release

A well-done press release must not overcome 6/8 thousands characters and it must contain two statements maximum. The news you want to communicate must be clear. To obtain a good press release the “news” is in the first three lines, respecting the 5Ws rule (Who, What, When, Where, Why, and then How in text body).

Aclima is in charge of sending to the people in charge with the communication of each partner at least 3 press releases in English (one per year), which will match with project milestones. These contents will be adapted to each region and sent to the local media. Each pilot must send at least 2 press releases to the media per year a total number of 6 per pilots (24 in the project). These should be sent to Aclima, and also the impacts generated.

It is suggested, as far as possible, to provide press releases with images / photos related to what is communicated. In addition, it is advisable to introduce a paragraph related to the project and its participants.

8.3. Official Website and pilot website

The website has a key role in the project. It will be WASTE4THINK showcase. It should speak not only to European Commission and technical stakeholders, but also to a large audience and media. For this reason, it has to contain not only records of information about pilots and projects, but also news, videos, photos. It must be social and communicative. Thus, it shall be always updated with appointments, documents, videos, photos and materials for media (by Aclima).

A well updated website shows the success of the project, otherwise the actions seem stopped and not finished. Furthermore, all the links to partners' websites give more opportunities to the users to find information and to deepen into project's contents. Website must be multilingual: a full version in English www.waste4think.eu (edited by ACLIMA) with a block about the details of the project and the descriptions of pilots and partners, and a block about news, social networks and events.

The web sections dealt with pilots actions should be edited by partners involved in Greek, Italian, Portuguese and Spanish (ES, GR, IT, PT).

Each partner should have a brief description of the project on its corporative website and a link to the general WASTE4THINK website.

Regardless, and since the web is one of the fundamental tools for the dissemination of the project, **the collaboration and involvement of partners, especially the one of the pilots is extremely important.** In order to update the contents of the web, it is important to follow a protocol to facilitate the work of both partners and those responsible for communication and so that all the information is collected.

The protocol is as follows:

The responsible for communication of each partner must complete the Annex 1 'Contents delivery' **every time they carry out an action to be considered newsworthy. The Annex 1 must be completed not only in English, but also in its local language.** Aclima will upload these news provided by the partners to the project website.

As stated above (see section 3. 1. Interaction between WP4, WP5 and WP7), it is important to create synergies between WP4 (innovative social actions) and WP7 (communication and dissemination) so that the work is not duplicated. In order to do so, the information in Annex 1 could be used to create a new sheet of 'Qualitative Reporting' about Pilot's Social Actions within WP4 by the coordinator of the Social Action Programme, BCN with the available information.

Thus, it is important to make it clear in Annex 1 if it is whether a new of dissemination or a Social Action (there is a section at the end of the Annex 1 where it can be chosen). If the social Action option is marked, Aclima will send the Annex 1 to BCN and BCN will decide if a new sheet is created and sent to the pilot to be completed or an existing sheet will be updated.

8.4. Newsletter

Newsletter is a collection of short news. Usually the right number is 3-5 items each newsletter.

The news must be short, 6/7 lines maximum, always respecting the 5Ws rule. There must always be a link to WASTE4THINK website, adding a URL where the user can find more information about the specific news. This tool will be used with the main aim to improve networking activities and disseminate appointments and hot news. Periodical newsletters (at least 2 per year, at least 6) will be edited in English (by Aclima) and all the partners will share them with a mailing-list of contacts collected during the project execution and from networking activities. It will be possible to receive WASTE4THINK newsletter directly by a subscription on the website, that includes an informed consent (ensuring Personal Data Protection law).

8.5. Social networks

Nowadays social networks are extremely useful as communication tools. Moreover, lots of people read articles and deepen through social networks, not directly on newspaper or television.

Aclima will provide contents in English for social networks related to the project (Twitter, Facebook y LinkedIn). Partners will be invited to contribute with posts in their language, following explicit and strict instructions:

Twitter & Facebook

It would be desirable that each partner who has accounts on Twitter and Facebook made at least two tweets per month with the hashtag of the project: #WASTE4THINK including photo and content related to the project: meetings, outreach activities. It is also recommended that partners retweet those tweets sent from WASTE4THINK profile in order to serve as amplifiers.

The responsible of communication for the pilots will have an important role in Twitter since this social network, apart from publicizing the project, aims to determine the views of users of the 4 pilots. Their involvement will be needed both for responding to questions and comments and to start discussions. From Aclima the inquiries arisen will be resend to the people in charge with the communication.

A minimum of one tweets per week will be published by Aclima. As regards to Facebook, it will be weekly updated.

LinkedIn

It is a very useful instrument for professionals talking to each other. There will be promoted a group inside the network to share expertise, news and information among partners.

The more active we are in the networks the more dissemination of the project we will achieve. More information in the Social Media Plan (see *Annex 4*).

8.6. Promotional materials

Aclima will be responsible for providing the following communication materials to the partners of the Project: **brochure, leaflet, posters, roll-up with public presentation, ppt template for general project**, then each WP leader will add their specific pilot presentation and this template will be used to prepare different presentations depending on its purpose. The general

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video will be available in the website of the project. The materials will be in English and editable formats will be also provided to the pilots so they will edit them in their respective languages. Merchandise materials are also going to be produced for the final event of the project (ISWA 2019).

These materials will be used by the partners in communication activities such as events, workshops, conferences, etc. and their production will be done with ecological materials.

The material will be checked first by the partner in charge of the specific activity. The changes will be sent to WP leader, later to all the partners involved in the WP “check” and finally to all the partners. At the end of the process, the ultimate version of the material will be edited.

Publication	Partner	Target group	Frequency
Communication plan	Legambiente	Partners	1
Entity's official websites	All	General public	1
Newsletter	Aclima	Stakeholders	6 (2 every year)
Social media	Aclima	General public	
Video	Aclima	General public	1
Awareness activities in school	Pilots	Students	1
Posters presentations	All	Stakeholders	
Brochure	Aclima	General public	1
Pilot's brochure	Aclima	General public	1 for each pilot
Regional press releases	Pilots	Journalists	6 (2 every year, 4 pilots)
English press releases	Aclima	Journalists	3
Press conferences	Pilots	Journalists	1
Tour for journalists	Pilots	Journalists	1
Scientific articles and publications	Pilots	Academics and scientific	1

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		community	
Workshop	Pilots	Stakeholders	1

Video is a very powerful tool, that could answer to several objectives, such as to raise awareness, to engage, to promote the project solution... The production of promo videos can spread the project messages in a direct, fast and easy way. The video can be used in different contexts, such as public events, social networks, official websites, press releases. Three types of videos will be edited in WASTE4THINK project to reach several stakeholders: children, municipalities, companies, general public.

- One video describing the project, its objectives and expected impacts with a brief description of the four pilots. The partner in charge of producing this video is Aclima using graphic resources (Motion Graphic). The reason why this format was chosen is because it will be displayed on the home of the website and this format is very suitable for the website since animation helps to grab attention of users, keep audiences engaged, communicate quickly and concisely, gain understanding and make a lasting impression in the audience.
- Videos for the YouTube channel of the project. A selection of short videos related to the project objectives or similar issues in order to connect and provide value to a larger audience. All partners are responsible for producing these videos for the YouTube channel. They can be informative videos, explaining the general actions they are carrying out in the project or specific actions. Also about meetings or participation in events or testimonials videos of citizens, partners of the project and so on. In addition, YouTube channel will be used as a tool to relay live sessions.
- Finally, a third type of videos will be produced focused on the results of the project. The responsible of the eco-innovative solutions are in charge of making this videos with a freestyle but based on the guide Aclima is going to provide them with the elements that have to be described in the video. These videos have a more technical content and the objective is to disseminate the results of the project and the lessons learnt.

Videos in local language must include subtitles in English (the translation of the texts will be done by the video makers).

8.7. Events and scientific publications

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Participation in activities and events as well as scientific publications will be another tool for the dissemination and communication of the project. Besides workshops and local media, the project will take part in external events and scientific journals such as:

Name	Target Group	No. Attendees	Estimated Date
Smart Cities Expo Barcelona, Spain	Cities, industry on smart cities	3000	Yearly around September
Smart Cities and Communities meetings	Stakeholders, policy makers	200-500	
WasteEng Conference	Researchers, public authorities, companies	1.000 - 2.000	Bi-annual
International Symposium on Energy from Biomass and Waste	Researchers, public authorities, companies	1.000 - 2.000	Biannual
Ecomondo - the green technologies expo (main expo on waste) Rimini, Italy	Cities, policy makers, companies	100.000	Annual fair (November)
ISWA (International Solid Waste Association)	Researchers, public authorities, companies	>100.000	(Bi-annual, 2019)
LCA [avniR] Conference	Researchers, public authorities, companies	4.000	Annual meeting
Green Week	Stakeholders, policy makers, researchers	1.200	Annual meeting
Resource Event	Cities, industry, utilities, policy makers	2.000	Annual meeting
Fun and Serious Games. Bilbao Spain	Serious game developers and users	2.000	Annual meeting
Publications in international peer-reviewed journals (e.g. Science of Total Env., J. of Urban Management, Computers and Education, The J. of Env. Education, Waste Management and Research)	Researchers	-	-
Specialized journals (e.g. ACR+ Newslite, Equipamiento y servicios municipales...)	Technicians	-	-

Yearly by the end of February, each partner will send to Legambiente and ACLIMA a calendar of its events with numbers of attendees expected. All the media will be involved to disseminate the contents of the event.

8.7.1. Rules for scientific publications

According to Grant Agreement (GA), WASTE4THINK partners will have to provide open access to all scientific publications (including peer-review articles, conference proceedings, grey literature, etc.) generated during the course of the project. Moreover, they have to be stored in an Open Access repository integrated within the OpenAIRE infrastructure[1] (for example ZENODO[2]). Also, each publication should include the following acknowledgement:

This {book, article, paper, work, conference, ...} has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995. The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

If the publication has been written in other language than English, the disclaimer should be translated.

There are three steps on how to comply with the EC open access policies:

1. **Publish your article in the journal, conference or publisher of your choice.** The document should contain the previous disclaimer.
2. **Add your final peer-reviewed manuscript to an open access repository.** There are different options depending of the nature of the document and the infrastructure that your organization has:
 - a. *Open Access journal or conference (gold open access):* if the document has been published in an open access journal or conference probably it is already deposited in a repository integrated with the OpenAIRE infrastructure. Then proceed with Step 3. In case you cannot find the document while completing

Step 3 below, please use Option 2.b or 2.c.

- b. *Self-archiving (green open access):* in case the host institution of the author has an institutional repository for open access publications, the document should be uploaded

there. Most of institutional repositories are already integrated with OpenAIRE platform; in this case proceed with Step 3. If while completing Step 3 you cannot find the document please use Option 2.c.

- c. *Last archiving resort (Zenodo)*: if the two previous options could not be used, then the document should be uploaded to Zenodo. In this case, the following step could be skipped (as Zenodo will make it automatically).

3. Register your publication in OpenAIRE portal linking it with WASTE4THINK project[3].

Every partner is responsible of providing an open access option to every scientific document published. Moreover, the corresponding author of the document is responsible of correctly register the document in the project section at OpenAIRE. The coordinator will use only the information retrieved from this platform to complete the periodic project report. For this reason, it is important to periodically check whether the list of publications is completed and updated, and that all document listed are open access. In case the list is not completed after following the previous steps, notify to the OpenAIRE help-desk (please put in cc the coordinator).

[1] The OpenAIRE tool (<http://www.openaire.eu>) is embedded in the EC's project portal (CORDIS) and will help project partners to report project results and list of publications within the project (OpenAIRE provides you with a button that will automatically generate a publication list).

[2] Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is a research data repository. It was created by OpenAIRE and CERN to provide a place for researchers to deposit datasets.

[3]

https://www.openaire.eu/search/project?lang=en&projectId=corda_h2020::ce0c30a22d3b8465bbfde778be6f2021

9. Planning: operative checklist

		2016							2017											2018											2019												
		6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1
Actions:		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4			
D7.	Dissemination & Communication Plan																																										
Task	Communication and Dissemination materials																																										
	Logo																																										
	Identity Style guide																																										
	Templates (Word, PowerPoint)																																										
	Brochure																																										
	Factsheet																																										
	Poster																																										
	Roll-up																																										
	Editable Communication materials																																										
	Public presentation																																										
	Public summary																																										
	Newsletter																																										
	Press release																																										
Task	On-line tools																																										

9.1. Links

All Annexes and templates are available on the following links:

- Annex 1 `Contents delivery`: [Annex 1](#)
- Dissemination google doc: [Dissemination](#)
- Press release template: [Press release](#)
- Annex 3 `Corporate Identity Manual`: [Annex 3](#)
- Annex 4 `Social Media Plan`: [Annex 4](#)
- `Qualitative Reporting` about Pilot's Social Actions : [Template](#)

10. Updates and monitoring

Updates version of this Dissemination and Communication plan will be produced for each reporting period (M18, M30, M42) as written in Grant Agreement (GA), in order to fix the communication strategies to the activities carried out reports on the activities carried out.

From M6 to M18 Legambiente, as WP7 leader, will lead a work of match between the guidelines contained in the Communication and Dissemination Plan and the communicative action performed by the partners. Legambiente will collect suggestions and proposals from WP leaders and will update this document in order to solve any critical issues and to improve the Plan. Since strategies and tools included in this document are indicative, after one year of work in the project pilots will have produced their specific strategy in a individual communication plan, suitable with their own Country, media area and targets. Legambiente will monitor the activities carried out and suggest how to refine them.

In the update at M18 the document will be integrated with the contacts tables.

11. H2020 requests

All beneficiaries of the project are committed to follow the guidelines about the use of the EU emblem using it in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes.

11.1. How text shall be used in conjunction with the EU emblem to communicate about EU funding

The preferred option to communicate about EU funding is to write “Funded by the European Union” or “Co-funded by the European Union” as appropriate next to the EU emblem on the communication material where the EU emblem is used.

Basic rules

The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm. The name of the European Union shall always be spelled out in full.

The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana. **Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.**

The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not prescribed in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way.

The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.

The colour of the font should be reflex blue (same blue colour as the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

11.2. How the name of the EU programme shall be used in conjunction with the EU emblem to communicate about the support received under a particular programme emblem to communicate about EU funding.

The name of the EU programme shall only be used, if it is relevant for the intended target audience.

Basic rules

The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm. The name of the European Union shall always be used in conjunction with the name of the program or fund and it shall be spelled out in full.

The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana. Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.

The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not prescribed in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way.

The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.

The color of the font should be reflex blue (same blue color as the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995.

The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The EU emblem and reference to EU funding must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence (taking also into account the nature of the activity or object). Examples: for equipment and major results a sticker or poster, for an infrastructure a plaque or billboard. Depending on the kind of activity (see your Grant Agreement) this shall be done in various ways.

You can find the acknowledgement of the EU funding for the different kind of activities on the H2020 Online Manual, in the following link: ec.europa.eu

11.3. Promotion of EU programme by third parties

Promoters of EU programmes and funds should refer to the name of the programme in their communication without using a visual mark (logo).

If the use of a graphical mark is deemed necessary (e.g. for signposting on buildings), the EU emblem shall be used in conjunction with the name of the programme. The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem and the use of the font is not prescribed. The rules that have to be observed are the following:

- ✓ The recommended typeface to be used are Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma and Verdana. Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.
- ✓ The text should not interfere with the EU emblem in any way.
- ✓ The size of the text and the size of the EU emblem should be proportionate.

The EU emblem can appear on communication material produced by promoters of EU programmes. The placement of the EU emblem should not give the impression that the third-party promoter is part of the EU institutions. Therefore it is recommended to place the EU emblem well apart from the logo of the third-party organisation.

11.4. Administrative agreement with the Council of Europe regarding the use of the European emblem by third parties.

General principle

Any natural or legal person ('user') may use the European emblem or any of its elements, subject to the following conditions of use.

Conditions of use

The use of the European emblem and/or any of its elements is allowed, irrespective of whether the use is of a non-profit or commercial nature, unless:

- the use creates the incorrect impression or assumption that there is a connection between the user and any of the institutions, bodies, offices, agencies and organs of the European Union or the Council of Europe;
- the use leads the public to believe erroneously that the user benefits from the support, sponsorship, approval or consent of any of the institutions, bodies, offices, agencies and organs of the European Union or the Council of Europe;
- the use is in connection with any objective or activity which is incompatible with the aims and principles of the European Union or of the Council of Europe, or which would be otherwise unlawful.

Trade mark and related issues

The use of the European emblem in accordance with the conditions in the previous section does not mean consent to registration of the emblem or an imitation thereof as a trade mark or any other IP right. The European Commission and the Council of Europe will continue the monitoring of applications for registration of the European emblem or part thereof as (part of) IP rights, in accordance with the applicable legal provisions.

Legal responsibility

Any user that intends to use the European emblem or elements of it may do so on its own legal responsibility. The users will be liable for any abusive use and possible prejudice following from such use under the laws of the Member States or any third country applicable to them.

Right to pursue any abuse

The Commission reserves the right to pursue on its own initiative or on request by the Council of Europe:

- any use which does not comply with the conditions set out herein, or
- any use which the Commission or the Council of Europe deem abusive in the courts of the Member States or any third country.